

Bisphenol - A and Possible Harm to Human Health: Review Article

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ABSTRACT Bisphenol A (BPA) is a chemical widely used for the production of polycarbonates and resins and is found mainly in baby bottles, water pipes, ATM receipts due to thermal paper, food storage containers and plastic bottles. Impacts are significant for the population's knowledge, having a direct and indirect relationship on human health, since this chemical has the potential to migrate from packaging to food with temperature change, resulting in exposure to this product. chemical to the human being. Given the findings, it is evident that health inspection agencies should be alert to manufacturers of plastic products and seek alternatives through the development of technology that will replace the use of this compound. In addition, it is necessary to raise awareness of the population by changing habits and consumption patterns.

KEYWORDS Bisphenol A, Toxicity, Polycarbonates

Introduction

Many facilities and objects were created to be part of the daily routine of man and to assist him in his tasks. Some are helpful and beneficial while others are known to be toxic [1]. Among these creations, the fruit of human creativity, there are synthetic organic polymers of the macromolecular constitution (plastic) derived from petroleum [2-4]

From this point bisphenol is mainly based on phenols, in several versions, there is bisphenol A (BPA), bisphenol B (BPB), bisphenol AF (BPAF), bisphenol C (BPC), bisphenol E (BPE), bisphenol AP (BPAP), bisphenol P (BPP), 4,4-bisphenol F (4,4-BPF), bisphenol S (BPS), bisphenol Z (BPZ), tetrachlorobisphenol A (TCBPA) and benzylparaben (PHBB) [5]. BPA is a chemical used in the production of resins. Its annual global production is approximately 6.8 million tons [6].

Its composition is present in plastics such as baby bottles, mineral water carboys, also used in the food and beverage packaging and coating, water pipes, food storage containers, baby bottles, toys and medical equipment. And consumer electronics [7-10].

Biomonitoring studies of BPA concentration in human tissues, urine, blood and other fluids, together with toxicokinetics studies of human metabolism, confirmed the negative aspects of BPA exposure [11]. Given the importance of the subject, in this article, we review the evidence on possible damage to human health by exposure to BPA-based polymers.

Methodology

The present work consists of a bibliographic review of the exploratory qualitative approach that addressed the use of BPA and the possible damages to human health. The concepts analyzed were: toxicity and its potential impact on direct toxicity and bioaccumulation in humans.

Human toxicity

Exposure to BPA has become a global public health concern as humans are increasingly exposed through their daily consumer activities. BPA is very sensitive to temperature variation and can be released from plastics in the sunlight or by heating a microwave, contaminating food and other products [12].

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Humans are chronically exposed to low doses of oral and dermal BPA-based polymers [11, 13,14]. First, upon ingestion there is rapid absorption and rapid first-pass metabolism in the intestine and liver, being completely absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract, not extensively metabolised by phase I reactions, but rapidly conjugated with glucuronic acid (metabolism). from phase II) to the non-active (BPA glucuronide) in the intestinal wall and liver, succeeding during biotransformation a distribution in the body [9]. Dermal, BPA dermal absorption occurs from thermal paper receipts, but the pharmacokinetics of BPA after dermal exposure are not understood [15].

These doses, although at low levels, promote endocrine disruptive action, causing changes in hormones such as estrogen (female sex hormone), androgens (male sex hormone) and thyroid hormones, inhibiting endocrine-hormonal binding [7,9,16]. In this follow-up, it is very harmful in women, because this compound has the potential to cause polycystic ovaries, endometriosis, breast cancer, ovarian cancer, as well as men, being able to cause prostate cancer, testicular cancer, delayed puberty, among other problems [12].

Besides, they are active during fetal, neonatal development. At fetal age, BPA can cross the placenta and concentrate in amniotic fluid. Fetuses and neonates are likely to be exposed to BPA from maternal sources as well as from environmental sources after birth. Its effect on organ development and differentiation depends not only on dose but also on early prenatal exposure [17-19].

Conclusion

Given the findings, it is evident that health inspection agencies should be alert to manufacturers of plastic products and seek alternatives through the development of technology that will replace the use of this compound. Also, it is necessary to raise awareness of the population by changing habits and consumption patterns.

Conflict of interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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